

Our fourth Newsletter is out!

Dear Reader,

Welcome to the latest edition of our newsletter, where we are thrilled to present the culmination of months of groundbreaking research and innovation within the SiComb consortium!

Key achievements include CNRS's exceptional performance with the in-house designed and manufactured HWCVD reactor, enabling precise control over the production of top-quality SiC thin films. Additionally, FAU's success in fabricating 3C-SiC at 1120°C on Si and SOI substrates signifies a significant breakthrough in SiCOI fabrication. Furthermore, DTU/POLITO's collaboration resulted in the optimization of micro-ring resonator fabrication processes, showcasing reduced propagation loss and enhanced characterization capabilities.

Looking ahead, we are excited to invite you to upcoming events such as the SiComb webinar, scheduled for March 27, 2024, which will delve into knowledge transfer for impactful interdisciplinary research.

Enjoy the read!

The SiComb Team

SiComb & SiC Nano for PicoGeo Final Conference

Innovation and business potential of SiC optical and mechanical materials: the experience of SiComb & SiC Nano for PicoGeo frontier projects

On March 20th, Brussels hosted the final conference marking the culmination of the SiComb and SiC Nano for PicoGeo projects, both of which represent significant strides in silicon carbide (SiC) research. Supported by the Horizon 2020 FET-Open Programme, these projects have set new benchmarks in developing compact, high-efficiency devices and advanced geophysical monitoring systems. The conference provided a platform for discussing the impressive outcomes of these initiatives and contemplating the future of SiC technology.

The poster features a central 3D illustration of a mountain range with a volcano-like peak, set against a dark blue background. The mountain is rendered in shades of red and purple, with glowing blue lines suggesting geological or technological structures. In the foreground, there are silhouettes of electronic components and circuitry. The overall aesthetic is high-tech and futuristic.

SiComb & SiC Nano for PicoGeo FINAL CONFERENCE

*Innovation and Business potential of
SiC optical and mechanical materials:
the experience of SiComb & SiC Nano for PicoGeo
frontier projects*

20th March 2024
9:30 – 12:30 CET
Brussels and online

Funded by
the European Union

Led by Dr. Haiyan Ou from the Technical University of Denmark (DTU), the SiComb project aimed to develop the first-ever on-chip frequency comb using SiC, noted for its remarkable optical properties and compatibility with existing CMOS technologies. The initiative has been a testament to the power of collaboration between academia and industry, showcasing the potential of SiC in various applications, from telecommunications to medical analysis.

The event also featured discussions on the challenges and advancements in fabricating and characterizing SiC, emphasizing its role in MEMS applications and integrated photonics.

Three Round table sessions delved into the critical phases of prototyping and risk management, sharing insights from various experts on overcoming hurdles and highlighting the significance of interdisciplinary collaboration in bringing theoretical innovations into practical use.

A particularly forward-looking discussion revolved around bridging the gap between research outcomes and market needs, with insights into potential applications beyond geophysics and the importance of knowledge transfer and digitalization in promoting sustainable innovation.

In closing, the conference underscored the invaluable contributions of all partners involved in these projects and looked ahead to future collaborations and research opportunities. The dedication and collective effort of the participants have paved the way for further advancements in SiC technology, promising a future where the boundaries of optical applications and geophysical exploration are continually expanded.

Revolutionizing Thin Film Production: CNRS Unveils Cutting-Edge HWCVD Reactor

At CNRS, the brand-new hot-wire chemical vapor deposition (HWCVD) reactor, entirely designed and manufactured in-house, has been tested and is fully operational. Its outstanding performance in independently controlling the various process parameters will ensure the development of top-quality SiC thin films. The filament can be heated to over 2200°C , the substrate support heated to 800°C , and the distance between the two can be precisely adjusted. Low-pressure conditions enable comfortable monitoring of the gas-phase deposition reaction in Si-C-H chemistry.

Picture of the HWCVD reactor chamber

Picture of the reactor operation through the optical windows. The intense radiation comes from the hot wire.

Chemical Vapor Deposition of 3C-SiC on SOI substrates at 1120°C

SiC is a key component in the developing field of (opto)electronic applications, and in particular SiC-on-insulator (SiCOI) substrates enable the development of innovative photonic applications and new devices for electrical switches. Therefore, the fabrication of SiCOI is of great interest and has already been demonstrated at temperatures above 1200°C. In order to maintain the complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor compatibility and to avoid diffusion of the buried SiO₂ layer, a process temperature below 1200°C is required.

In the last few months of the project, FAU has achieved significant results in the fabrication of 3C-SiC by CVD at 1120°C on Si and SOI substrates. The epitaxial growth of 3C-SiC was achieved using a horizontal cold-wall CVD reactor with a non-water-cooled inner setup. Silane and propane, diluted in hydrogen, were used as precursor gases for the silicon and carbon sources. After conducting various tests on Si substrates, a C/Si ratio of 6.8 was chosen due to the reduction in carbon species splitting at lower temperatures, as compared to temperatures above 1200°C. The only difference between the substrates is the extended cool-down period, which is necessary to prevent delamination of the epitaxial layer from the SOI substrate.

SEM image of a 533 nm thin crystalline 3C-SiC layer with a smooth surface on SOI substrate.

The successfully grown 3C-SiC layers were characterized by SEM imaging, EDX, Raman, and X-ray diffraction (XRD). The cross-section SEM image shows a 533 nm thick 3C-SiC layer with a smooth surface and no voids beneath the grown layer.

The results achieved in the project in recent months were published in crystals under the title “Fabrication of SiC-on-Insulator (SiCOI) Layers by Chemical Vapor Deposition of 3C-SiC on Si-in-Insulator Substrates at Low Deposition Temperatures of 1120 °C” and presented at the DKT2024 in Erlangen.

In recent months, some growth runs with methane instead of propane have also been carried out with promising results, which will be continued in the future.

Breaking Boundaries in Silicon Carbide Photonics: DTU's Innovations and Future Prospects

Researchers at DTU, are optimizing the fabrication process flow of high-quality-factor micro-ring resonators by focusing on methods to reduce material absorption, enhance sidewall smoothness and improve uniformity of silicon dioxide cladding for amorphous SiC waveguides. Our approaches include annealing PECVD-deposited a-SiC, low-temperature oxidation and chemical treatments for improving sidewall smoothness, and tuning recipe parameters in PECVD for depositing SiO₂. Currently, the propagation loss we have achieved in PECVD-deposited a-SiC waveguides is reduced from 9 dB/cm to 7 dB/cm by optimizing process flow.

At DTU, we have now implemented a customized thermo-electric controller unit, designed and optimized by our project team at PoliTo, into our microcomb characterization setup. This TEC unit helps us to control the temperature and characterize microcomb. This integration will further enhance our ability to characterize and study the thermal effect on SiC-based frequency combs.

Zoom-in image of the TEC sample holder in a chip test setup

(a) Schematic experimental setup for the generation of frequency comb.

DTU has recently submitted an invited paper titled “4H-SiC Microring Resonators: Opportunities for Nonlinear Integrated Optics” to APL Perspectives, presenting new frequency comb results and prospects. In addition, the DTU team will participate in the upcoming Conference on Lasers and Electro-Optics (CLEO 2024, USA) to globally present further research achievements and progress made in the SiCOMB project. Moreover, a feature article entitled silicon carbide photonics invited by Compound Semiconductor Magazine will be published in issue 3, 2024. Driven by the good results already achieved in SiComb, DTU will continue the effort for more and bigger breakthroughs in future by self-arranged resources.

Synergies in ecosystems for emerging materials and technologies

The EU FET Open (Pathfinder) type of projects is characterized by that there is development from early idea stage. In case of SiComb: new materials concept for an emerging technology. The manufacturing is then essential for the next development stages. New materials development is a common feature in most cutting-edge high-risk and ground-breaking interdisciplinary EU research projects.

In SiComb, the innovation partner Alminica AB is active in transfer of knowledge for emerging technologies from advanced materials and manufacturing. As part of SiComb activity, Alminica has explored how a larger context such as regional economic growth (such as smart specialisation strategy) align with technology development and create synergies. Their combination creates a type of materials ecosystem. The smart specialisation strategy by European Commission is a place-based innovation policy concept to support regional prioritisation in innovative sectors, fields or technologies through the entrepreneurial discovery process.

That technology and larger context situation aligns with other emerging silicon carbide ecosystems, such as India.

It is recognized that India has the potential to be a major player in the semiconductor area, but they need to overcome challenges in manufacturing to compete globally. India had good progress in the semiconductor manufacturing until 1990s. India faced setbacks in maintaining its semiconductor manufacturing edge from the 1990s onwards. As example, the polysilicon for solar face a challenge to catch up while in recent years there are investments. Now, there is new push by the "Make in India" and "India Semiconductor Mission".

ALM participated at the International Conference on Emerging Semiconductor Materials and Applications (ICESMA) during 8th - 10th March 2024 organized by the Centre for Materials for Electronics Technology (C-MET) that is a premier R&D organization under Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MeitY), Government of India, Hyderabad, India. Besides giving a keynote lecture, Dr. Mikael Syväjärvi was part of panel to discuss the new evolution of India silicon carbide ecosystem, and shared learnings from SiComb transfer of knowledge activity.

Some insights in this will be shared at the upcoming SiComb webinar.

SPOTLIGHT

SiComb webinar “Transfer of knowledge for impact creation in cutting-edge high-risk and groundbreaking interdisciplinary research.”

March 27, 2024 at 10-12 AM.

A challenge in FET Open / Pathfinder projects which are based on new materials growth concepts is that the device development stage has to wait for suitable material. In turn, the application development has to wait for suitable devices. Three years pass quickly. In this webinar we will share our experiences in developing frequency comb applications as well as what we have learned from transfer of knowledge activity to promote creation of impact in cutting-edge high-risk and groundbreaking interdisciplinary research.

REGISTER NOW

Open webinar for research to business by the digitalization for future competitiveness

March 26, 2024 at 10-12 AM.

The digitalization is a key for the future. The silicon carbide goes from raw material and growth to an application that is in a system (for example electric vehicles and being part of an energy context). That is a supply chain (stakeholders linked with each other). The chain can be optimized by sharing data between the links. Any emerging technology that can present a shared data scenario will have a competitive advantage and long-term effect. The positioning includes tokenization (Web3 wallets) and digital twins. Alminica has developed during SiComb concepts of the future values by digitalization and invited experts for an open webinar on March 26 at 10AM to share the insights.

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Thanks for your attention!

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all the latest SiComb news!

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